

PRODIGEES

Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe

Towards Sustainable Development

D4.4. Launch/Update of Online Repository for Digital Knowledge Products

Project Acronym	PRODIGEES
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Zenodo

PRODIGEES utilises Zenodo as its online repository for Digital Knowledge Products (DKP), presentations, works-in-progress and publications. Zenodo was created by researchers of the OpenAIRE project and CERN. OpenAIRE was established under the aegis of Open Science and Open Data policies for research funded by the European Commission (EC). Zenodo allows OpenAIRE and CERN to actualise their goal of broadening access of publication data and software to more people in more places. Making note of the ‘digital revolution’, OpenAIRE and CERN built Zenodo after recognizing that access to data and software differed per nation and per community. Zenodo is part of an Open Science movement which seeks to make sure that no one falls behind in the information age.

Zenodo allows users to create research communities. Researchers can deposit research data into the research community. A designated curator examines the data and decides whether the data will enter the repository or not. For Grant Agreement 873119, we created the “PRODIGEES Research Community” (<https://zenodo.org/communities/prodigees/>), where the curation is facilitated by the PRODIGEES Project Manager of the coordinating institution, the German Development Institute / Deutsches Institut für Entwicklungspolitik (DIE). Data can be uploaded

to the PRODIGEES Research Community as a publication, poster, presentation, dataset, image, video/audio file, software, lesson, physical object or other file type. Upon submission, the deposited data is immediately assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) number. The data is given the “Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International” license by default, which establishes it as Open Access. The other options for labelling the data with contributors, keywords and descriptors are numerous, allowing the data to be recognised through general and specific search queries.

While PRODIGEES has and will continue to foster peer-reviewed publications throughout the course of the project, it is a project built to inspire and catalyse research in digitalisation and sustainable development that continues after the lifetime of the researchers’ individual secondments and even the project itself. Therefore, Zenodo’s value as an online repository for PRODIGEES is not only in its capacity to play host to peer reviewed publications, but also to be a repository for data sets, presentations, concepts and PRODIGEES’ DKP.

Open Science

Open Science (and thus Zenodo) is compliant with Horizon 2020’s FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) as well as the qualities which deem a work as Open Access. According to the EC’s website, Open Access is a fundament of the Horizon enterprise, while it is also only one element of Open Science. Other elements of Open Science include citizen science and open source software. The EC is actively steering its research programs towards the broader domain of Open Science.

PRODIGEES is a participant in Horizon 2020’s Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP). The ORDP mandates that all data produced by PRODIGEES remains Open Access. The data produced during PRODIGEES is social science data and, although interdisciplinary, does not work with genetic, biological nor technological data which may need restrictive patents. Therefore, all of the data produced by the PRODIGEES project is both Open Access and Open Science compliant.

Example of PRODIGEES Research Community on Zenodo (02 Dec. 2020)

zenodo Search [] Upload Communities benjamin.stewart@die-gdi.de

PRODIGEES Research Community

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November 12, 2020 (v1) Presentation Open Access View

Digital but still Unequal: The Challenges of Digitalisation for Emerging Powers - Mexico
 Domínguez, Carlos;
 Digitalisation and other exponential technological changes can bring important opportunities to tackle development challenges within the Agenda 2030 framework. However, without adequate policy interventions, the access to these technologies might be limited to a small number of people in ways that m
 Uploaded on December 1, 2020.

March 9, 2020 (v1) Video/Audio Open Access View

Can digital platforms be regulated? A Dialogue Between The European Union and México
 Schneider, Ingrid;
 Can digital platforms be regulated? A Dialogue Between The European Union and México This video presentation was produced as a Digital Knowledge Product for the Horizon 2020 MSCA RISE project, Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe towards Sustainable Development .
 Uploaded on December 1, 2020.

April 6, 2020 (v1) Other Open Access View

How the EU and rising powers can shape their future sustainably
 Grimm, Sven; Reiners, Wulf; Stewart, Benjamin;
 Digitalisation is a domestic issue as well as an imperative for international cooperation. Aiming to lead the transition to a healthy planet and a new digital world, the European Commission published a vision, goals and priority areas on how to shape Europe's digital future in February 2020. T
 Uploaded on December 1, 2020.
 Published in The Current Column: .

July 16, 2020 (v1) Journal article Open Access View

Democratic Governance of Digital Platforms and Artificial Intelligence? Exploring Governance Models of China, the US, the EU and Mexico
 Schneider, Ingrid;
 The article addresses the digital transformation and new power asymmetries and challenges to democracy by the world's seven largest digital platforms. Four different governance models are examined: The Chinese authoritarian model, the libertarian US-model, the European regulatory model, and th
 Uploaded on December 1, 2020.
 Published in JeDEM, vol. 12, Issue 1: .

More

New upload

Community

PRODIGEES

PRODIGEES Research Community
 PRODIGEES stands for **Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development**. PRODIGEES is a Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action - Research & Innovation Staff Exchange (MSCA-RISE) research project which receives European Union funding. The project is coordinated via the German Development Institute / Deutsches Institut für Entwicklungspolitik's (DIE) Managing Global Governance (MGG) programme as its digitalisation work strand. The research focus is digitalisation towards sustainable development in the context of transnational knowledge cooperation and training.
 The PRODIGEES consortium includes:

- Austrian Academy of Sciences - Institute of Technology Assessment (OEAW-ITA), Austria
- Centre for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS), Indonesia
- Fundação Getúlio Vargas (FGV), Brazil
- German Development Institute / Deutsches Institut für Entwicklungspolitik (DIE), Germany
- Instituto Mora (MORA), Mexico
- Istituto Affari Internazionali (IAI), Italy
- Luiss Guido Carli University (LUISS), Italy
- Research and Information System for Developing Countries (RIS), India
- Stellenbosch University (SU), South Africa
- Universität Hamburg (UHAM), Germany

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